

Desiccation-Tolerant Rhizobacteria Maintain their Plant Growth-Promoting Capability after Experiencing Extreme Water Stress

^{1,4}Laura Abisaí Pazos-Rojas, ¹Osvaldo Rodríguez-Andrade, ^{2,5}Ligia Catalina Muñoz-Arenas, ^{1,6}Yolanda Elizabeth Morales-García, ³Andrés Corral-Lugo, ^{1,7}Verónica Quintero-Hernández, ¹Antonino Baez, ^{1,6}Dalia Molina-Romero, ^{*1}Jesús Muñoz-Rojas

¹Laboratorio de Ecología Molecular Microbiana (LEMM), Centro de Investigaciones en Ciencias Microbiológicas (CICM), Instituto de Ciencias (IC), Benemérita Universidad Autónoma de Puebla (BUAP), Puebla, México

²Facultad de Ingeniería Ambiental, Universidad Popular Autónoma de Puebla

³Institut de Biologie Integrative de la Cellule, Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique, Paris, France

⁴Centro de Investigación en Biotecnología Aplicada, Instituto Politécnico Nacional, Tepetitla, Tlaxcala, México

⁵Centro Tlaxcala de Biología de la Conducta, Universidad Autónoma de Tlaxcala

⁶Facultad de Ciencias Biológicas, BUAP, Puebla, México

⁷CONACYT, LEMM, CICM, IC, BUAP

Abstract

Bacteria from rhizosphere have the potential to promote the growth of plants, and could be used as inoculants to increase the crop profitability. However, under drought stress conditions, the number of bacteria associated to seeds could decrease below the minimal number of bacteria required to obtain a positive plant response. At the present work, the capability of 28 rhizospheric bacterial strains to tolerate 18 days of air desiccation stress (at 30°C and 50% of relative humidity) was evaluated. Results showed different levels of bacterial tolerance and five categories were proposed based on the bacterial survival ratio to air desiccation (BSRad): highly tolerant bacteria (BSRad>80), tolerant (60<BSRad≤80), middle tolerant (40<BSRad≤60), low tolerant (20<BSRad≤40), and very low-tolerant (BSRad≤20). Highly tolerant and very low-tolerant bacteria were selected to inoculate maize seeds. After inoculation, seeds were subjected to desiccation conditions for 18 days and then sown in sterile vermiculite and watered with MS solution. Only highly tolerant strains were able to survive associated to seeds under desiccation conditions keeping their beneficial traits such as, bacterial adherence, colonization and plant growth promotion. In contrast, the very-low tolerant bacterial strain was not able to colonize the rhizosphere nor promote the growth of the plants. Tolerant bacteria to desiccation have desirable traits in comparison to non-tolerant bacteria, because they could be more stable in powder presentations of inoculants without need of protectants, they could survive with higher numbers in soils with low water availability keeping their ability to promote the plant-growth until the end of adverse conditions; when the seed germination take place.

Keywords

Bacterial Inoculants; Survival Bacteria; Bacterial Desiccation; PGPR; Beneficial Bacteria

Introduction

Bacteria are responsible for several important process in the environment [1-4], most of them are harmless or often beneficial for their host. Some beneficial properties widely studied comprise the plant growth promotion [5-7], bioremediation of xenobiotic compounds by rhizobacteria [8, 9] biocontrol of pathogens [10-12], and production of compounds of industrial interest [13, 14].

Bacteria face adverse circumstances in their habitats, for example changes of pH, water availability,

***Corresponding author:** Jesús Muñoz-Rojas, Laboratorio de Ecología Molecular Microbiana (LEMM), Centro de Investigaciones en Ciencias Microbiológicas (CICM), Instituto de Ciencias (IC), Benemérita Universidad Autónoma de Puebla (BUAP), Puebla, México. E-mail: joymerre@yahoo.com.mx; Tel: +222 2295500

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osmotic stress, changes in temperature, low availability of nutrients and others. Environments with low water activity involve salinity and desiccation stress. Tolerant bacteria to low water activity could be more competitive under such stress conditions, thus strains with high salinity [15-17] and desiccation [18, 19] tolerance performed better than non-tolerant. Studies of tolerance to desiccation for beneficial bacteria such as *Bradyrhizobium japonicum* [20], *Rhizobium leguminosarum* [21], *Pseudomonas putida* mt-2 [22], *Pseudomonas putida* KT2440 [23], *P. putida* GAP-P45 [24], and *Azospirillum brasilense* Sp7 [18] have been performed.

Desiccation is defined as drying below 0.1 g H₂O g⁻¹ dry mass ($\leq 10\%$ water content [WC]). This is roughly equivalent to drying to equilibrium with air at 50% relative humidity and 20°C [25]. Desiccation is different from drought. Drought is the lack of water availability in the environment of an organism, whereas desiccation is the loss of water of cells until reach equilibrium with the water vapor present in the air; which means extremely low water content inside cells [26]. Desiccation always causes cellular metabolism to cease, while in drought conditions the cellular activity never stops, however a partial loss of the water from cells is possible [27]. Desiccated tolerant bacteria can recover their physiological activities after rehydration [26, 28].

Bacterial tolerance to desiccation is an important trait for soil applications because the low water availability decreases the bacterial survival and consequently the number of bacteria able to perform the plant-growth promotion or remediation. Thus, the low water availability of soil decreased the Rhizobia population introduced into the field in just four hours [20]. In the present study, the capability of beneficial bacteria to tolerate air desiccation was explored. Both high tolerant bacteria and sensitive bacteria were inoculated in maize seeds, and subjected to desiccation during 18 days; after this time only tolerant bacteria were detected associated to seeds. Tolerant bacteria were able to colonize the rhizosphere and promote the plant growth of maize, but this was not observed for sensitive bacteria.

Material and Methods

Bacterial Strains

Strains used in the present work are listed in table 1. These strains were selected by their ability to promote the growth of plants and/or the capability to bio-remediate soils [18, 29-39]. All strains were able to growth in

MESMA medium [40] at 30°C and their morphology after desiccation process was corroborated in selective culture media (Table 2) [18, 29-31, 38, 41-43].

Desiccation Air Experiments

Bacteria were grown in MESMA liquid medium at 30°C and shaken at 200 rpm until reach the stationary phase. The pellet was washed twice and suspended in the same volume of distilled water. Forty aliquots of 500 μ l of each bacterial suspension containing approximately 9X10⁸ bacterial cells/ml were placed in Eppendorf tubes of 1.5 ml of capacity. The tubes containing the samples were kept opened but covered with sterile cotton to avoid contamination. After register the initial weight, tubes containing samples were subjected to desiccation at 30°C and 50% of Relative Humidity (RH) for 18 days. Every 3 days, five samples were weighted to determine the water lost in the samples. For these same five samples, the bacterial number and the bacterial survival ratio to air desiccation (BSRad) were determined. Samples with incomplete desiccation (day 3) were supplemented with the necessary volume of distilled water to reach the initial 500 μ l of bacterial suspension. In the case of complete desiccation (days 6 to 18), 500 μ l of distilled water were added to the tubes to reach the initial volume of bacterial suspension. The supplemented water was mixed with the dried cells by pipetting up and down several times, and after 20 min, with occasional shaking, the re-hydration was achieved. Bacterial suspensions were serially diluted and viable cells counted on selection media plates (Table 2) by the massive stamping drop plate method (MSDP) [44]. Bacteria survival ratio in air (BSRad) was calculated similar to the BSR for freeze-drying [18, 43, 45-47]. Thus, BSRad was defined at this work as the ratio of the log of the number of bacterial cells present in the suspension at any time post desiccation (PD) plus one to the log number of viable cells before desiccation (BD), all multiplied per 100; BSRad= $[(\log PD + 1)/\log BD] \times 100$. Therefore BSR of 100 means that all bacteria survive after the stress and BSR of 0 means that none bacteria was able to survive.

Surface Sterilization of Maize Seeds

Autochthonous blue maize seeds collected from a field located in the region of Tlaxcala, Mexico [18] were submerged in ethanol 70% during 30 seconds, washed with sterile distilled water and submerged in sodium hypochlorite 1.5% during 20 minutes [29]. After this, maize seeds were washed 8 times with sterile distilled

Table 1: Strains Explored in this Work

Strain	Source of isolation	Beneficial characteristic	Reference
<i>Enterobacter</i> sp. UAPS03001	Maize rhizosphere	PGPB	Morales-García et al., 2011
<i>Bradyrhizobium</i> sp. MS21	Nodule of <i>Amicia zygomeris</i>	PGPB	Donated by Antonio Munive
<i>Bradyrhizobium</i> sp. MS22	Nodule of <i>Trifolium repens</i>	PGPB	Molina-Romero et al., 2017
<i>Bradyrhizobium</i> sp. MS23	Nodule of <i>P. coccineus</i>		
<i>Acinetobacter</i> sp. EMM02	<i>Amicia zygomeris</i>		
<i>Burkholderia tropica</i> MTo-293	Maize rhizosphere	PGPB	Reis et al., 2004
<i>Burkholderia tropica</i> MOc-725	Maize rhizosphere		
<i>Burkholderia tropica</i> Ppe8	Sugarcane rhizosphere		
<i>Burkholderia unamae</i> MT1-641	Maize rhizosphere	PGPB	Caballero-Mellado et al., 2004
<i>Burkholderia unamae</i> MCo-762	Maize rhizosphere		
<i>Burkholderia unamae</i> SCCu-23	Maize rhizosphere		
<i>Burkholderia sacchari</i> LMG 19450	Sugar cane soil		
<i>Burkholderia silvatlantica</i> SRMrh-20	Maize rhizosphere	PGPB	Perin et al., 2006
<i>Gluconacetobacter dizotrophicus</i> PA1 5	Inner tissues of sugarcane	PGPB	Muñoz-Rojas and Caballero-Mellado, 2003
<i>Azospirillum brasilense</i> Sp7	Grass rhizosphere	PGPB	Terrand et al., 1978
<i>Azospirillum lipoferum</i>	Grass rhizosphere		
<i>Azospirillum amazonense</i>	Grass rhizosphere	PGPB	Baldani et al., 1997
<i>Azospirillum halopreferans</i>	Grass rhizosphere	PGPB	Reinhold-Hurek et al., 1987
<i>Sphingomonas</i> sp. GOF 203	Rhizosphere soil from grasses	Bioremediation of Lindane	Böltner et al., 2008
<i>Sphingomonas</i> sp. OF178	Bulk soil		
<i>Sphingomonas</i> sp. ANS 245	Bulk soil		
<i>Sphingomonas</i> sp. DS 204	Bulk soil		
<i>Sphingomonas</i> sp. GOF 202	Rhizosphere soil from grasses		
<i>Sphingomonas</i> sp. ANS 285	Bulk soil		
<i>Klebsiella</i> sp. T19A	Inner tissues of sugarcane	PGPB	Rosemblueth et al., 2004
<i>Klebsiella variicola</i> T29A	Inner tissues of sugarcane		
<i>Pseudomonas putida</i> KT2440	Tomato rhizosphere	Bioremediation of aromatic compounds	Nakasawa, 2002
<i>Pseudomonas putida</i> DOT1E	Wastewater	Bioremediation of aromatic compounds	Ramos-Gonzalez et al., 2001

PGPB means Plant Growth Promoting Bacteria

Table 2: Selection Media used for Bacterial Growth

Strain	Culture Media for morphology corroboration	Reference
<i>Enterobacter</i> sp. UAPS03001	LB Ap (50 µg/ml) and E (50 µg/ml)	Morales-García et al., 2011
<i>Bradyrhizobium</i> sp. MS22	LB Gm (50 µg/ml)	This work
<i>Bradyrhizobium</i> sp. MS21		
<i>Pseudomonas putida</i> DOTT1E	LB Cm (100 µg/ml)	Ramos-González et al., 2001
<i>Azospirillum brasilense</i> Sp7	Congo Red	Rodríguez-Caceres, 1982
<i>Azospirillum amazonense</i>		
<i>Azospirillum lipoferum</i>		
<i>Azospirillum halopreferans</i>	Congo Red CRO (50 µg/ml)	Molina-Romero et al., 2017
<i>Acinetobacter</i> sp. EMM02	BAC CTX (30 µg/ml)	
<i>Bradyrhizobium</i> sp. MS23	LB-bromotymol blue (75 µg/ml)	This work
<i>Sphingomonas</i> sp. GOF 203	LB 5%-benomyl (500 µg/ml)	This work
<i>Sphingomonas</i> sp. OF178		
<i>Sphingomonas</i> sp. ANS 245		
<i>Sphingomonas</i> sp. DS 204		
<i>Sphingomonas</i> sp. GOF 202		
<i>Sphingomonas</i> sp. ANS 285		
<i>Gluconacetobacter dizotrophicus</i> PA1 5	LGI	Muñoz-Rojas et al., 2005
<i>Burkholderia unamae</i> MTI-641	BAC	Caballero-Mellado et al., 2004
<i>Burkholderia unamae</i> MCo-762		
<i>Burkholderia unamae</i> SCCu-23		
<i>Burkholderia silvatlantica</i> SRMrh-20		
<i>Burkholderia sacchari</i> LMG 19450		
<i>Burkholderia tropica</i> MTo-293	BAC	Reis et al., 2004
<i>Burkholderia tropica</i> MOc-725		
<i>Burkholderia tropica</i> Ppe8		
<i>Pseudomonas putida</i> KT2440	MM9-Citrate Cm (100 µg/ml)	Muñoz-Rojas et al., 2006
<i>Klebsiella</i> sp. T19A	McConckey Ap (30 µg/ml)	This work
<i>Klebsiella variicola</i> T29A		

water. Surface sterile maize seeds were used for the inoculation experiments.

Inoculation of Bacteria on Maize Seeds and Desiccation

Three strains with different level of tolerance to desiccation were grown until stationary phase in 30mL of MESMA liquid media and washed two times as described before. Bacterial suspensions were used to inoculate maize seeds, 60 axenic seeds were soaked in each bacterial suspension for 1 h. Maize seeds soaked in sterile water were used as controls. After this, seeds of each treatment were placed on sterile filter paper inside plastic dish plates. Plates were placed without tops inside chamber of desiccation at 30°C and 50% RH for 18 days, maintaining the sterile conditions. Five seeds of each treatment were used to evaluate bacterial number adhered to surface before and post-desiccation. Five replicates of inoculated seeds and controls subjected to desiccation were placed individually in 3 ml of water during 20 min to rescue the bacteria and count their numbers by the MSDP method in selective media (Table 2).

Colonization of Resistant Bacteria and Plant Growth Promotion

The rest of seeds subjected to desiccation, of each treatment, were sowed in Falcon tubes containing 5 g of sterile vermiculite and watered with 25 ml of MSJ1 liquid solution [29]. All tubes were placed in a growth plant chamber with photoperiod light/dark 16/8, temperature 28°C/25°C and 80% of RH. Plants were grown during 15 days and rhizospheric bacteria colonization was evaluated as previously described using five replicate plants for each treatment [48]. Briefly, the vermiculite adhered to the roots, considered as the rhizosphere was re-suspended in water in proportion of 1:10 (w/v) [18, 39, 48]. This suspension was vortexed at 3000 rpm for 3 min. The resulting suspension, which was considered to contain bacteria from the rhizosphere, was serially diluted. The numbers of bacteria were determined by the MSDP method using a selective media.

The fresh and dry weight of plants was evaluated. Fifteen plants of each treatment were extracted from the tubes at 30 days after sowing. Plants were washed and dried with adsorbent paper, the fresh weight of plants was registered. Plants were chopped into small pieces, dehydrated at 70°C for four days, and weighed. Data of each treatment were compared with the Student's t-test,

using Sigma Plot of the Jandel Scientific Software. Results of comparison were used to generate a matrix of differences and similarities between treatments for assignment of letters [18, 48].

Results

Bacterial Tolerance to Air Desiccation

Water loss of samples occurred gradually between 0 to 5 days after the beginning of desiccation (DABD) at 30°C and 50% (HR) (Figure 1); we considered this period as drought conditions for bacterial cells. After 6 DABD, bacteria were considered completely desiccated because all samples were reduced to powder and reached constant weigh; indicating that the maximum water loss, for such conditions, had occurred (500µg) (Figure 1). Therefore, at 0 DABD cells are hydrated and desiccation has not happened, at 3 DABD cells are losing water (during desiccation), at 6 DABD or more, cells were completely desiccated.

The 28 strains explored showed different levels of tolerance to desiccation (Table 3). Based on the results we proposed five categories according to the tolerance to desiccation: highly tolerant bacteria ($BSR > 80$), tolerant ($60 < BSR \leq 80$), middle tolerant ($40 < BSR \leq 60$), low tolerant ($20 < BSR \leq 40$), and very low-tolerant ($BSR \leq 20$). For example, *Enterobacter* sp. UAPS03001 resulted a highly tolerant bacterium, *K. variicola* was tolerant, *B. tropica* Ppe8 showed middle tolerance, *Klebsiella* sp. T19A showed a low tolerance and *B. sacchari* LMG 19450 showed very low tolerance (Figure 2, Table 3).

Bacterial tolerance to desiccation was not an exclusive characteristic of one specific species, in fact strains of the same species showed different levels of desiccation tolerance (Figures 3 and 4). For example, *B. unamae* comprises a highly tolerant strain (MTI-641), a low tolerant strain (MCo-762) and a very low tolerant strain (SCCu-23) (Figure 3). In the same way *B. tropica* comprises a highly tolerant strain (MTo-293), a middle tolerant strain (Ppe8) and a very low tolerant strain (MOc-725) (Figure 4).

Bacterial Tolerance to Desiccation Associated To Maize Seeds

Tolerant bacteria might have advantages over the sensitive strains when they are associated to seeds under desiccation conditions, to explore this idea, three

Figure 1. Loss of water in desiccation assays of *P. putida* KT2440. Values were calculated by subtracting the weight of the Eppendorf tubes after desiccation to the weight of the tubes before desiccation. Desiccation assays were assayed at 30°C and 50% HR. Each point represents the media of 5 determinations with the respective standard deviation.

Figure 2. Bacterial Survival Ratio to air desiccation (BSRad) of representative strains with different levels of tolerance: 1) *Enterobacter* sp. UAPS03001; a highly tolerant (blue line), 2) *Klebsiella variicola* T29A; tolerant (green line), 3) *B. tropica* Ppe8; middle tolerant (yellow line), 4) *Klebsiella* sp. T19A; low tolerant (orange line), and 5) *B. scchari* LMG 19450; very low tolerant bacterium (red line). DABD means days after the beginning of desiccation.

Figure 3. Bacteria survival ratio to air desiccation (BSRad) of *Burkholderia unamae* strains: 1) MTI-641 (blue line), 2) Mco-762 (orange line), and 3) SCCu23 (red line).

Figure 4. Bacteria survival ratio to air desiccation (BSRad) of *Burkholderia tropica* strains: 1) MTO-293 (blue line), 2) Ppe8 (yellow line), and 3) MOC725 (red line).

Figure 5. Survival of bacteria associated to seeds of maize during an experiment of desiccation (30 °C; 50% HR). Each point represent the media value of 5 determinations with the respective standard deviation. *Enterobacter* sp. UAPS03001 (blue line), *Klebsiella variicola* T29A2 (green line), and *B. sacchari* (red line). DABD means days after the beginning of desiccation.

bacterial strains with capability to adhere and colonize maize [29] and with different level of tolerance to desiccation were selected. These bacteria were the highly tolerant (*Enterobacter* sp. UAPS03001), tolerant (*K. variicola* T29A), and very low tolerant (*B. sacchari*). We hypothesize that *Enterobacter* sp. UAPS03001 and *K. variicola* T29A could survive better under desiccation stress associated to seeds and consequently colonize better the roots of plants. After inoculation, maize seeds were subjected to desiccation (30°C; 50% HR) for 18 days. Under this condition, water was completely lost since the first day (data not shown). As we expected *Enterobacter*,

sp. UAPS03001 was the most tolerant strain (Figure 5). *K. variicola* T29A was tolerant but the number of bacteria at the end of the experiment was lower than that for *Enterobacter* sp. UAPS03001. In association to seeds, *B. sacchari* was very sensitive to desiccation; in fact, this bacterial strain was not detected since 3 days after the beginning of desiccation contrasting with air desiccation experiment where bacteria decline to undetected numbers since 12 DABD (Table 3). Apparently, conditions of desiccation in association to seeds were more aggressive than desiccation conditions of the bacterial suspension.

Table 3: Survival of Bacteria Subjected to Different Time Periods of Desiccation Stress (BSRad)

Strain	DABD						
	0	3	6	9	12	15	18
<i>Enterobacter</i> sp. UAPS03001	100	98.1 ±2.85	99.96 ±3.0	94.05 ±1.61	88.72 ±1.26	86.46 ±1.13	84.33 ±1.88
<i>Azospirillum halopreferans</i>	100	87.94 ±3.96	87.80 ±8.23	86.07 ±3.29	86.01 ±2.73	83.06 ±2.73	81.34 ±2.05
<i>Bradyrhizobium</i> sp. MS22	100	95.38 ±2.22	88.48 ±1.95	87.76 ±2.35	91.07 ±1.78	84.07 ±3.21	81.88 ±2.69
<i>Bradyrhizobium</i> sp. MS02	100	88.67 ±2.39	88.41 ±3.29	88.14 ±2.20	88.0 ±1.74	88.10 ±1.76	88.05 ±3.82
<i>Bradyrhizobium</i> sp. MS21	100	99.31 ±1.69	92.82 ±1.96	92.59 ±1.77	88.20 ±2.59	86.58 ±2.94	86.01 ±1.25
<i>Burkholderia unamae</i> MTI-641	100	100 ±3.18	100 ±3.02	93.66 ±1.86	93.73 ±0.53	92.42 ±3.54	83.65 ±4.05
<i>Burkholderia tropica</i> MTo-293	100	99.54 ±0.62	88.28 ±1.95	86.64 ±1.06	86.17 ±0.37	83.22 ±3.21	80.08 ±1.97
<i>Gluconacetobacter dizotrophicus</i> PAI 5	100	102 ±2.96	99.79 ±3.65	95.49 ±5.65	94.68 ±2.13	90.97 ±2.29	80.85 ±5.66
<i>Pseudomonas putida</i> DOT1E	100	100 ±0.95	100 ±0.90	99.08 ±2.18	87.31 ±1.19	81.34 ±1.94	74.77 ±1.78
<i>Azospirillum brasilense</i> Sp7	100	95.98 ±2.47	89.53 ±3.21	85.42 ±3.53	85.31 ±1.72	83.77 ±0.98	75.11 ±3.56
<i>Azospirillum amazonense</i>	100	96.42 ±1.51	94.28 ±3.54	84.72 ±2.25	81.35 ±1.53	78.92 ±3.39	75.13 ±1.75
<i>Klebsiella variicola</i> T29A2	100	93.60 ±7.66	92.10 ±4.81	80.90 ±7.57	75.60 ±4.98	70.10 ± 6.5	70.5 ± 1.2
<i>Bradyrhizobium</i> sp. MS23	100	86.27 ±1.06	85.66 ±1.93	79.63 ±3.04	78.98 ±3.06	78.47 ±1.81	74.20 ±2.83
<i>Sphingomonas</i> sp. GOF 203	100	98.29 ±0.96	88.08 ±1.94	72.78 ±1.79	72.40 ±1.73	72.93 ±1.07	71.36 ±1.70
<i>Sphingomonas</i> sp. OF178	100	96.68 ±2.43	82.38 ±2.94	73.06 ±2.60	70.65 ±3.17	70.06 ±1.95	69.05 ±4.5
<i>Sphingomonas</i> sp. ANS 245	100	92.96 ±2.76	92.08 ±3.36	74.91 ±5.34	72.65 ±1.56	71.86 ±2.83	67.99 ±3.12
<i>Sphingomonas</i> sp. DS 204	100	93.47 ±0.86	88.23 ±5.0	73.34 ±0.95	67.56 ±1.58	67.45 ±3.31	64.62 ±6.1
<i>Sphingomonas</i> sp. GOF 202	100	99.98 ±0.48	94.82 ±5.67	66.98 ±2.10	63.46 ±3.03	63.79 ±6.38	62.78 ±9.11
<i>Azospirillum lipoferum</i>	100	78.79 ±2.89	68.86 ±3.03	67.54 ±3.03	67.90 ±3.22	67.30 ±2.29	62.76 ±2.21
<i>Burkholderia silvatlantica</i> SRMrh-20	100	101.82 ±1.30	81.62 ±6.30	81.12 ±3.73	71.53 ±2.18	50.76 ±1.87	50.80 ±5.65
<i>Sphingomonas</i> sp. ANS 285	100	99.99 ±2.15	80.09 ±1.32	69.42 ±1.57	65.65 ±1.90	62.01 ±6.65	58.20 ±11.88
<i>Burkholderia tropica</i> Ppe8	100	100 ±1.52	85.40 ±5.37	71.45 ±3.96	69.38 ±3.65	62.36 ±4.52	51.21 ±0.82
<i>Burkholderia unamae</i> MCo-762	100	100 ±4.50	75.08 ±4.26	75.01 ±4.42	61.81 ±3.98	57.94 ±6.23	30.07 ±8.62
<i>Klebsiella</i> sp. T19A	100	89.60 ±5.04	37.40 ±3.75	20.80 ±7.02	19.80 ±6.85	20.40 ± 9.7	20.0 ± 3.5
<i>Burkholderia sacchari</i> LMG 19450	100	100 ±3.86	69.76 ±2.99	43.00 ±9.23	0	0	0
<i>Pseudomonas putida</i> KT2440	100	94.94 ±5.09	43.34 ±7.66	20.39 ±8.06	0	0	0
<i>Burkholderia unamae</i> SCCu-23	100	99.98 ±0.93	60.10 ±0.17	0	0	0	0
<i>Burkholderia tropica</i> MOc-725	100	94.01 ±3.15	50.54 ±2.56	0	0	0	0

DABD means days after the beginning of desiccation. Values represent the media of five independent determinations and the respective Standard Deviation. Colours were assigned with base in categories proposed based on the survival bacterial ratio to air desiccation (BSRad) observed highly tolerant bacteria (BSRad>80) (Blue), tolerant (60<BSRad≤80) (Green), middle tolerant (40<BSRad≤60) (Lemon yellow), low tolerant (20<BSRad≤40) (Dark yellow), and very low tolerant to desiccation (BSRad≤20) (Red).

Tolerant Bacteria and their Capability to Maintain Beneficial Characteristics after Rehydration

The capability of bacteria to conserve beneficial characteristics after the desiccation process and rehydration was evaluated. For this, inoculated seeds were dried during 18 days and sowed in vermiculite. We include control seeds desiccated without any inoculated bacteria. Fifteen days after sowing in vermiculite, the ability of bacteria to colonize the rhizosphere of plants was screened. Only tolerant and highly tolerant bacteria were detected associated to the rhizosphere of maize plants in high numbers (Figure 6). However, *B. sacchari* was not

detected in the rhizosphere of plants and control plants were free of rhizospheric bacteria. In addition, plants from seeds inoculated with tolerant bacteria (*Enterobacter* sp. UAPS03001 or *K. variicola* T29A) showed higher fresh and dry weight (Figures 7, 8), in comparison to control plants or plants from seeds inoculated with *B. sacchari* LMG 19450. The appearance of plants also was better in plants inoculated with tolerant bacteria (data not shown). Therefore, tolerant bacteria survive to desiccation and maintain its ability to colonize the rhizosphere of plants and promote the growth of plants.

Figure 6. Bacteria colonizing the rhizosphere of maize (15 days after sowing): 1) *Enterobacter* sp. UAPS03001 (blue bar), and 2) *Klebsiella variicola* (green bar). Bacteria were desiccated during 18 days in association to maize seeds and planted in humid vermiculite.

Figure 7. Fresh weight of plants inoculated with *Enterobacter* sp. UAPS03001 (blue bar), *K. variicola* T29A2 (green bar), *B. sacchari* (red bar), and non-inoculated plants (gray bar). Different letters in the graphic means that there are statistic differences between treatments. Data represent media of 15 plants.

Figure 8. Dry weight of plants inoculated with *Enterobacter* sp. UAPS03001 (blue bar), *K. variicola* T29A2 (green bar), *B. sacchari* (red bar), and non-inoculated plants (gray bar). Different letters in the graphic means that there are statistic differences between treatments. Data represent media of 15 plants.

Discussion

Bacteria have faced desiccation events since ancestral times [25, 26], and several of them could tolerate this stress because they have been selected under low water availability. Tolerant bacteria has been isolated from extreme environments like deserts [49], and saline places [50]. Nonetheless, bacteria with the ability to tolerate desiccation could be located everywhere, because in almost all environments there are periods were water could be absent, in this way, bacteria can be desiccated under these conditions and tolerance to desiccation result a fundamental characteristic to bacterial survival. Freeze-drying is an effective method to preserve bacteria for long term [51]. However, we did not use freeze-drying but air desiccation, because our goal was not to preserve but subject bacteria to a close related stress faced by microbial inoculants during soil desiccation. Several beneficial bacteria are able to promote plant growth and/or bioremediate toxic compounds from the environment [52]. In our work, the tolerance to air desiccation of 28 beneficial bacterial strains isolated from different environments was explored. None of these strains was isolated from deserts, nor saline or extremal environments. However, some of them were highly tolerant to desiccation such as *Enterobacter* sp. UAPS03001, *Bradyrhizobium* sp. MS02, *Bradyrhizobium* sp. MS21, and *Burkholderia unamae* MTI-641 and other bacterial species showed different levels of tolerance to desiccation. Different levels of tolerance to desiccation were reported in other works [20, 53]. For example, *Gluconacetobacter diazotrophicus* PAI 5 R can resist 2

days of desiccation [54], while *Bradyrhizobium japonicum* tolerates only some hours during extreme desiccation [20]. In order to classify the levels of bacterial tolerance to desiccation we proposed five categories based on the results (highly tolerant bacteria, tolerant, midway tolerant, low tolerant, and very low tolerant). We found out that tolerance to desiccation is not exclusive of one bacterial species or genus, it is distributed in all microorganisms [55]. In fact, the analysis of tolerance to desiccation with strains of *Burkholderia tropica* showed three levels of tolerance (Figure 3).

The water availability in some places of the earth is restricted due to climatic changes [56] and tolerant bacteria to desiccation could be more effective to carry out plant growth promotion or rhizoremediation in places with low water availability [18, 52, 57]. Bacterial survival on inoculated seeds is affected under low water availability and consequently colonization was diminished for *Bradyrhizobium* sp. [20]. In the present work, tolerant bacteria to air desiccation were selected, inoculated on maize seeds and subjected to desiccation during 18 days, only tolerant strains were able to survive associated to seeds under desiccation conditions. In addition, these tolerant bacteria showed good rhizospheric colonization and positive plant growth promotion when seeds were sown and grown in vermiculite. Therefore, the selection of tolerant bacteria is a promising alternative to increase the effectiveness of plant-growth promotion and could increase possibilities to increase efficacy for bioremediation [18, 52, 58]. Although, tolerance to desiccation could

be increased with addition of a protectant like alginate, sugars, polyalcohols and others [43, 59, 60] high tolerant bacteria are desirable for both, the formulation of stable bacterial inoculants in powder presentations without need of protectants and they also could survive with higher numbers associated to seeds in soils with low water availability keeping their ability to promote the plant-growth until the end of adverse conditions; when seed germination begins.

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